

What's next?

Exploitation Roadmap and Intellectual Property Report - midterm

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- 1 PU = Public
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Abbreviations

IP	Intellectual property, refers to all kinds of creations of the mind within our project.
ER	Exploitation roadmap, refers to activities after our project has finished.
KER	Key exploitable results

Summary

Task 4.4 is about the Exploitation Roadmap and Intellectual Property Report – midterm, where exploitation refers to activities after our project has finished and we understand intellectual property (IP) as all kinds of creations of the mind within our project.

This deliverable outlines the strategy that entails:

- An analysis of opportunities for exploitation in science, policy and society
- A planning of next steps to fully exploit result
- A proposal and a roadmap for partners' joint exploitation in terms of organisation (partnership and governance) and promotion activities;
- A definition of the IP strategy considering the IP (methodologies, know-how, tools, etc.)
- An identification of potential risks in the exploitation, understanding their impact and anticipating corrective actions.

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Figure 1 Illustration of Miro working board

1. Aims of the Exploitation Roadmap and Intellectual Property Report - midterm

1.1 Aims

This roadmap elaborates on BIOTraCes' plans to exploit its results after the project has finished. By setting up an exploitation roadmap, we make concrete use of the project's results in further research and innovation activities other than the ones covered by the project. Exploitation can be for scientific, societal and policy making purposes. Intellectual Property (IP) management is necessary to ensure all data in this project are protected by intellectual property rights in the correct way.

1.2 Methodology and activities

This exploitation roadmap was developed in a collaborative process within the consortium. Two exploitation workshops were hosted (April & June 2024), where at least one representative of each partner was present. In the first workshop, the main expected results and ideas were harvested on exploitation of each research partner as well as exploiting BIOTraCes as a whole. Questions that were answered by participants are:

- What are the main expected results on research partner level?
- What are the main expected results of BIOTraCes as a whole?
- What are your plans for exploiting results of the project after BIOTraCes has finished?
- What could we aim for regarding joint exploitation?

Results were categorized in insights, methodology, networks and theory. Preliminary exploitation plans, based on these results were identified and categorized in plans relevant for exploitation in science, policy and society. In order to identify the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) participants could vote for particular results that they perceive as impactful, low risk exploitable (low hanging fruits) and/or innovative. In the workshop, the online whiteboard tool [Miro](#) was used, to enhance the possibilities to exchange ideas (Figure 1). Results from the first workshop were used to draft a first version of this deliverable. In the second workshop, the emphasis was on implementation of the ideas that were harvested in the first workshop. The participants were asked, again with the aid of MIRO, to give input on the exploitation strategy, on information on risks, values and impact per KER and draw up an exploitation plan per Key Exploitable Result. After the second workshop this document was finalized by the task leaders and peer reviewed and complemented by the partners.

Figure 1 Illustration of Miro working board. A selection of the frames that participants worked on during workshop 1.

1.2.1 IP management methodology

Background IP mapping

In the consortium agreement, all partners signed the following statement: *"It is agreed between the Parties that, to the best of their knowledge, no data, know-how or information of each partner is needed by another Party for implementation of the Project (Article 16.1 and its Annex 5 Grant Agreement, Section "Access rights to results and background", sub-section "Access rights to background and results for implementing the action") or Exploitation of that other Party's Results (Article 16.1 and its Annex 5 Grant Agreement, Section "Access rights to results and background", sub-section "Access rights for exploiting the results"). This represents the status at the time of signature of this Consortium Agreement."*

Foreground IP mapping

The two exploitation workshops were also important steps in the IP management process. In the first workshop (April 2024) all foreground IP (results) were identified at two levels: BIOTraCes project level, and research partner level (See Chapter 2).

During the second workshop some questions on IP rights regarding these results were raised and discussed.

2. Results & Key exploitable results

Chapter 2 is dedicated to results and Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the BIOTraCes project. We view a Key exploitable result as a project result that: 1. Has societal/ academic/ policy/ commercial¹ relevance 2. Can be exploited as a stand-alone result. Results were selected as KERs on the basis of their degree of innovativeness, their high impact and their exploitability. The results and KERs are identified at two levels: results & KER that are relevant for BIOTraCes as a whole (2.1) and results & KER that are important for each partner individually (2.2). Perhaps some of the latter can be in common for several partners.

Owners and exploiters of the KER will be all consortium partners. For each research partner and their individual KER, they are the owner.

Figure 2 Possible KERs. This picture was used in the workshops to inspire participants (Westerink, 2024)

2.1 KER and Results of BIOTraCes as a whole

The key exploitable results (KER) and results have been categorized under Insights, Methodology, Networks and Theory. Some KER might fit into multiple categories, in that case the most applicable was selected. Results are listed, while KERs are underlined.

¹ Although we view commercial relevance as key exploitable, it is not relevant for exploiting our results, as we as a project do not focus on the business sector.

Insights

- Demonstration and implementation of processes of transformative change in 9 EU case studies.

The demonstration will provide insights on the transformative potential of initiatives (biodiversity innovations), the barriers they encounter and how they can be leveraged. It provides us with cross-cultural examples which show the diversity in the EU; case studies from several member countries show insights on biodiversity loss, recovery and best practises. These different cases will improve our knowledge of specific and generalizable contextual factors which support biodiversity innovations.
- Knowledge on biodiversity interdependencies in SDGs.

Methodology

- A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a diversity of stakeholders. These plural methods and tools aim to generate knowledge while promoting democratic participation including marginal groups/ identities/ perspectives in decision making regarding biodiversity issues. This includes intersectional approaches for transformative governance.
- A set of methodologies to investigate transformative change, including participatory research.
 - o New approaches to (biodiversity/ societal value) monitoring.
 - o Methods for co-development of ToTCs with stakeholders.
- Tools to translate a ToTC into policies
- Showcase how working according to the PEPE (pluralizing, empowering, politicizing and embedding) principles works.

Networks

- Transdisciplinary learning community/ network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity
 - o Support scientists in developing more effective interventions by working on interdisciplinary projects.
 - o Network of EU researchers and practitioners carrying out work on, or with an interest in transformative change for biodiversity.
 - o Interconnect the different case studies partners to motivate the creation of a strong network with a shared key goal in transformative change for biodiversity.
- EU-interproject collaboration working towards a joint understanding of transformative change for biodiversity/ a just and nature positive society.

Theory

- Theories of transformative change, including values, power relations, enabling actors.
 - o Leverage points (opportunities) identified for positively disrupting systems; identification of obstacles and how these can be navigated.

- The Handbook will contain guidance for co-producing ToTCs for different contexts, in the terms of concepts, analytical methodologies and cooperation practices
- Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change

2.2 Results per partner

During the workshops, the following results were harvested that the partners expect, here presented per partner:

Insights

- UBB:
 - A set of data (open access in Zenodo) about the intention to have a touristic biocultural experience in a HNVf area.
 - Conceptual terminology: "biocultural touristic experience".
- BC3:
 - enhanced knowledge regarding (urban) biodiversity challenges in the educational community and how to include it in the education curriculum, understanding barriers to successful project implementation at the municipal level.
- CER:
 - Herder techniques, tricks on videos.
- CES:
 - Contributions towards new techniques for soil restoration and management through collective intelligence and community participation.
 - Mutual learning regarding co-governance processes and their contribution towards regenerative territories beyond the very community we are working with.
- UGOT:
 - Small scale private forest owners' views on biodiversity; potential for alternative perspectives and approaches to forest land use and management based on local knowledge and attention to individual and contextual factors.
- MRU:
 - Knowledge/practical tools on how to include all interested parties (e.g. policy makers, communities, NGOs) in the river dam removal process.
- UNICT:
 - Improved understanding how agriculture and energy production interplay through the use of water.
- UT:
 - Knowledge about commons and the model of the Community Land Trust (CLT), participatory processes like Joint Fact Finding, and participatory workshops with stakeholders.
 - Critical discussion on (biodiversity) monitoring strategies and mapping of different socio-political definitions / understandings of biodiversity .

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- WR:
 - o Theories of transformative change for nature inclusive building.
 - o Insights into transformative change that can be used in teaching.

Methodology

- BC3:
 - o Evaluation and knowledge generation regarding co-production processes across different institutional departments and schools/educational community.
 - o
- CES:
 - o Contributions towards theoretical and methodological connections between transformative change and intersectional lenses, intertwining environmental and social justice.
- UGOT:
 - o Mixed methods with interviews (including walking interviews during field research), archival research (e.g. historical maps), GIS analysis.
- MRU:
 - o Protocols/ manuals for those working with river dam removal on how to do that in the inclusive way. Of particular importance is creation of the space for expression of plural attitudes, values, ideas, etc..
- UNICT:
 - o Triangulation of different methodologies to ensure that data are gathered and analysed at sufficient qualitative and quantitative depth, in the context of transdisciplinarity. I.e. mixing quantitative modelling with an ethnographic approach.
 - o Experimenting soundscapes and more than human life histories in a collaborative way, through PAR, and making these tools available for ecomuseology.

UT:

- o Insights on employing creative participatory methods and knowledge co-creation.
- o 'Tools' for understanding translation processes between different types of knowledge (and also understanding translation processes between theory and action), including the use of theories from aesthetic humanities to understand change processes & how these may be supported through artistic collaborations.
- UBB:
 - o Community-based causal effect analysis (CBCEA), a participatory method, derived from community-based system dynamics. CBCEA helps the understanding of complex community dynamics and relationships between direct and indirect causes and effects of a selected problem.

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Networks

- CER:
 - o Establishing herder's school; integration of results into other trainings; find and join international training opportunities.
- CES:
 - o Contribution for fine-tuned decisions intertwining local food production and services of providing meals in Social Economy organisations and schools in the community.
- MRU:
 - o Consultation hub(s) in academy or within policy making institutions for those seeking knowledge on inclusive river dam removal process.
 - o Courses (e.g. university) for biodiversity specialists on how to work inclusively with communities in the process of river dam removal.
- UNICT:
 - o A platform and methodology based on evidence and practice for local communities and the university to cooperate.
 - o Supporting disenfranchised groups in having a voice in political processes and decision-making by cutting the distances between civil society organizations and people pushed to the edge.
 - o Critical elaboration of the concept of innovation in relation to the concept of biodiversity. Specifically, an attempt to produce an innovative definition that incorporates both innovation and biodiversity.
- UT:
 - o A researcher network around Foodpark Amsterdam.
 - o A mobile method for activating community engagement and involvement in Foodpark Amsterdam and generate related / FPA inspired initiatives.
- WR:
 - o Contacts/community of key players on nature inclusive building in the Netherlands.
 - o Support for/ empowerment of societal stakeholder.
- UBB:
 - o The definition of "biocultural touristic experience", to be shared with farmers, policymakers, and conservationists to enhance their understanding of the biocultural aspects of HNV farming and facilitate the implementation of practices that preserve biodiversity and cultural heritage.
- UGOT
 - o Developed and strengthened network and connections between social scientific forest research and societal stakeholders (government agencies; associations, commercial actors; land owners); to some degree on a general level and particularly in the three geographical study areas in Western Sweden.
- BC3
 - o Strengthened relationships and networks between institutional actors and educational community on the local level.

Theory

- BC3:
 - o Connection of theories of transformative change with urban planning literature (urban innovation/experimentation) and education studies.
- UGOT:
 - o Small-scale private forest owners' views on biodiversity, competing claims on land, prerequisites stemming from local current and historical factors as well as the owner's priorities, enabling and constraining conditions. We will highlight alternative perspectives on small-scale forest management and develop theoretical contributions based on locally grounded in-depth case study research.
- MRU:
 - o Academic material (handbooks, monographs) on best community involvement practices in river dam removal process.
- UT
 - o Deepening understanding on Transformative Change processes including the role of art-science collaborations, transdisciplinary and action-based research in these processes.
- WR:
 - o Theory of transformative change specific for nature inclusive building in The Netherlands.
- UNICT:
 - o A conceptual and inspirational toolkit to critically investigate *biodiversity* and *innovation* through their mutual relations.
- MRU:
 - o Integrate the knowledge of multiple values and attitudes towards river dam removal from various stakeholders into river biodiversity preservation theory.

2.3 KER and their beneficiaries/users, value proposition, risks and expected impact

2.3.1 KER and their beneficiaries and users

Table 1 KER and their beneficiaries and users

No.	Preliminary Key Exploitable Results	Beneficiaries / users
1	Theories of Transformative Change, including values, power relations, enabling actors	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN), EU policy makers, Scientific community, Grassroots organisations
2	A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN), EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society, Nature organisations, Cultural groups, Scientific community, local institutions

3	Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies	Policy makers at the regional and national level in member states of case studies
4	Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change	EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society
5	Transdisciplinary learning community / network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN), EU policy makers, Civil society, Scientific community, education institutions

2.3.2 KER and their value proposition

The value proposition describes the value for society, policy and environment and their benefits for beneficiaries and users.

1. Theories of Transformative Change (ToTC), including values, power relations, enabling actors

This KER provides more nuanced lenses to interpret and analyse the interconnectedness of environmental and social dimensions, which is of great value to the scientific community. It contributes to a system of concepts, methods and practices that support interactions and translation at the science-policy interface working on more sustainable futures.

Furthermore, this KER helps policy makers to be able to devise and plan what could happen as a result of strategies and interventions. Moreover, it is about translating ToTC to more effective and just interventions and strategies that policy makers could use. When policy makers incorporate this knowledge to develop transformative governance, it should be able to detect the connection between environment-related material constraints and processes of othering, which benefits public bodies and communities.

2. A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders

This KER is relevant to a wide range of stakeholders. It allows the finetuning of interventions by different types of actors to boost transformative change without leaving behind marginal and subaltern groups and provides practical propositions for how to horizontalize decision-making.

3. Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies

This KER provides a grounded and in-depth understanding of empirical transformation processes, which contributes to empirical evidence to be used by the scientific community. This will also benefit policy makers at all levels, who will get an increased understanding of the consequences of certain policies on different (local, regional national) levels.

4. Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change

By empowering local communities to take the lead in nature conservation and sustainability projects, e.g., community supported agriculture, biocultural tourism resilience and nature-inclusive housing, we provide trust in communities and their own capacity to solve problems and promote sustainability environmental stewardship of the local community. Civil society will benefit from this, starting with our own societal partners. However, this KER is also relevant to policy makers at all levels aiming for just transitions. Because of this KER, marginal perspectives, identities and groups will be better heard.

5. Transdisciplinary learning community /network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity

This KER builds on the connections that have been forged in BIOTraCes between scientists from various scientific disciplines, civil society actors, policy makers etc. across Europe. Being connected through networks of networks to others working on transformative change for biodiversity (including the linkages within the cluster of transformative Horizon projects and the networks represented in the Influencer & Stakeholder Board), this KER provides an important condition for future action. In addition, the experiences in BIOTraCes with reflection, co-production and learning are likely to become more standard practice through exchange in this learning community.

2.3.3 KER and their risks

Here follows a short description of the risks that will be faced per KER. These involve problems that can be encountered in the exploitation phase such as lack of time and money or competing theories. Strategies for prevention and mitigation are proposed.

1. Theories of Transformative Change, including values, power relations, enabling actors

A risk is societal resistance towards transformative change for biodiversity, for example related to the call to change lifestyles. A mitigating strategy includes adapting our language, adopting vocabulary with less 'triggering' potential and finding alternative stories.

2. A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders

By creating one roadmap of "how" to engage diverse communities we are under the risk of tokenism/ simplification of complex interactions and participatory processes, which will result in a range of methods and tools that are for example blind to certain inequality patterns or marginal groups/identities/perspectives. In addition, in spite of our focus on marginalized groups, through working with initiators and representatives there is always a risk of not addressing the community itself enough. We need to stress the importance of participatory methods for reimagining the use of the public spaces in terms of collective enjoyment and regenerative purpose.

3. Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies

As we are dealing with local cases of biodiversity conservation insights might be easily dismissed as too local with limited potential for transferability cross contexts. Evidence-based transformative changes cases can help mitigate the risks of conflicting 'ways of doing'; traditional versus innovative/collaborative.

4. Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change

A lack of support from the general public, in the form of money and interest, to support the strategies and commitment from the local community is a risk to develop this KER.

Moreover, the risks lie in the difficulties to make this strategies context or actor specific, to find balance between general strategies for EU level and specific strategies in certain contexts. This is conflicting with the risk mentioned under number 3; on the one hand, we need to find theoretically overarching insights that are relevant across many local contexts and scales. On the other hand, we also need to maintain attention to the specific level and how theoretical constructs can be applied in a meaningful way in unique cases. In some way, we need to find a balance in this.

5. Transdisciplinary learning community /network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity

A practical risk is busy schedules, which makes it difficult to find time for meetings. A possible solution could be to integrate activities of ideas cross-pollination into official schedules.

Another concern is that there are marginalized groups/identities/perspectives involved in the affected area of policies and sciences; how will and how can they react to involvement, especially at international level? Language may be a barrier. KER nr 4 will provide tools for a truly inclusive transdisciplinary learning community.

2.3.4 KER and their impact

This section describes the expected impact on society, policy, nature and scientific community after completion of the project per KER.

1. Theories of Transformative Change, including values, power relations, enabling actors

One impact is that transformative change/ the nature positive society will be discussed in various sectors of society (not only sustainability science and - policy). Next, more effective and just (public and private) interventions and strategies for bending the curve (addressing root causes) of biodiversity decline, finally resulting in the greatest goal and therefore impact; contributing to halting and reversing the negative development of biodiversity, and systemic changes.

2. A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders

The impact of this KER is awareness-building for the importance of participatory processes to achieve inclusivity, shifting the focus from project outcomes to cooperation practices.

3. Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies

We aim to increase valuation of these bottom-up initiatives and able to inspire policies that are able to support these.

Through cross-case analysis certain themes may emerge (such as landownership), that can be blind spots in current biodiversity policy creating inequalities and ineffective policies. Such knowledge would promote widespread co-governance and inclusive policies.

4. Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change

The impact of this KER is the enhancement of knowledge, awareness, interest of local people and general public, as well as more fair and inclusive policies through a higher awareness of justice pitfalls among policy makers. This way, the use of these strategies for propelling transformative change for biodiversity, will enable transformative policy innovation.

5. Transdisciplinary learning community/network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity

This KER could result in accelerating learning on transformative change for biodiversity, transformative science and transformative governance across networks of citizens, businesses, governments and scientists across Europe. This would lead to acceleration of policy innovation, lifestyle change, nature-based solutions and relevant and legitimate science, ultimately contributing to bending the curve of biodiversity loss towards biodiversity recovery.

3. Exploitation strategy

This deliverable outlines the exploitation strategy that will define scientific, policy and social objectives within a three - year horizon from project completion.

3.1 Exploitation in science

The exploitation in science can be expected in the form of publication activities, within the project as well as publications and projects. During the project, at least 15 publications in academic, peer-reviewed, open access journals are expected. These include publications with evidence-based research on how cultural issues and vested interests might impact environmental goals. Knowledge of such underlying (indirect) factors is equally needed as knowledge on the direct drivers of biodiversity loss. Moreover, BIOTraCes will provide knowledge on how to apply a broadened theoretical framework on transformative change and use this knowledge in additional papers and future research proposals (considering effective participation of marginalized communities and social justice goals as part of ToTC), hereby contributing to a line of research that involves continued knowledge development on transformative change for biodiversity.

The research articles and other publications can be shared through various communication channels (i.e. workshops) to raise awareness. Findings can also be used as teaching materials at universities (including, but not limited to, the BIOTraCes partners), as well as conferences and seminars.

Furthermore, researchers from BIOTraCes can contribute to a network of researchers that is developing around transformative change for biodiversity or can participate in science-policy-society interface networks such as the EU Science Service for Biodiversity.

On a research partner level, BIOTraCes' legacy can be continued through working together with other universities to write follow-up grants where our case studies are used as well. BIOTraCes has also established a cooperation between the 11 consortium partners, which can be (re)activated for future proposals and/or collaborations.

3.2 Exploitation in policy

The results from BIOTraCes can inform decisions for transformative change related to biodiversity and steer EU policies to be more attuned with the transition practices that the European Commission aims to stimulate. BIOTraCes' emphasis on the inclusion of marginalized groups/identities/perspectives and the importance of local context and knowledge within these policies will be particularly helpful.

Through collaboration with EU policy makers, we can contribute to EU policy recommendations on e.g. land use and alternative models of ownership (i.e. the commons, land trusts).

A clear exploitation in policy could be a policy briefing with a multiple scale scope, from national to EU level, to offer new imaginaries for policymaking, that go beyond the business as usual.

With a focus on the case studies, exploitation in policy covers writing policy briefs targeting specific policies based on our project findings, write policy recommendations & invitation for dialogue to improve local policy measures as well as specific high impact

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sector EU level policies, such as agricultural policies.

By becoming a stable partner in the regional and national policy processes taking place in the fieldwork areas, we can take next steps of co-creating policies. This could for example be WR in the province of Overijssel, the regional government they are cooperating with in their case study. Moreover we can demonstrate in workshops for policymakers, seminars and further scientific outputs how co-governance processes may improve and connect processes in urgent need of alignment.

3.3 Exploitation in society

The main objective is to create a horizontal relationship of trust between science and various actors in society. More specifically, the awareness of, visibility, and trust in the transformative change concept must be improved. By co-creating tools and strategies that can be used by societal organizations, they can improve their own theories of change.

The insights gained from our case studies can be used in various countries and other projects. For example, from BIOTraCes findings, other agroecology initiatives on national and EU level can be supported and improved. In particular, insights about leverage and empowerment can support bottom-up initiatives and biodiversity innovators in their transformative ambitions.

On a case level, BIOTraCes builds long term partnerships where relevant knowledge is exchanged, contributing to the creation of follow-up projects, as well as stimulating the empowerment and participation of stakeholders in social processes.

4. Tools, planning and organization

4.1 Preliminary exploitation plans per KER

This section describes how will each KER be exploited, which can be by 1 or more partners. These are not definite plans yet, however we aim to do the following activities per KER.

1. Theories of Transformative Change, including values, power relations, enabling actors

We plan to spread our gained knowledge in several ways. We can reach different audiences via different media, including using our transdisciplinary network of KER nr. 5 to spread the knowledge on theories of transformative change. Communication activities are already occurring while the project is ongoing, and we plan to continue and elaborate on the following ways of communication:

- Offering workshops to teach others on gained knowledge and our way of working according to the PEPE principles
- Podcasts and tools for youth people, women, etc... to reach non-conventional audiences
- Publish, be active on social media and go to meetings (preferably also outside scientific community)
- Storytelling in various ways, including visual forms

Next to these communication plans, we consider to write policy briefings "translating" ToTC into practical policy options, in particular if our contacts with the European Commission, national and regional governments invite us to do so. In addition, we will probably respond to calls and write proposals to develop our work in the scientific area.

2. A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders

Our exploitation plans include:

- Informing policy makers is to create an overview of methods and tools (e.g. in form of policy briefs based on our various Deliverables) that sensibilizes for the risks of universal processes. In such policy briefs we can suggest through good examples, our case studies, a set of different qualitative criteria to evaluate impact.
- Sharing experiences (good and bad) from methodologies applied in the project through story telling on social media.

3. Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies

- We aim to organize public talks or an online event, in collaboration with our influencer and stakeholder board, to present our findings to their networks.
- For policy makers, we plan to write a 'manifesto' or white paper or a snappy newspaper article, or a video by ESCI to inform them on our work and findings.
- Establish partnerships with public institutions at multiple scales to mainstream mechanisms boosting transformative change.

- Our societal partners have a big role in exploiting the results of the case studies: they can use the co-produced insights in their activities, their networking, influencing policy, and acquisition of funds.
- 4. Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change**
- Further using, disseminating and discussing these results and publications in other contexts; scientific conferences, meetings with national and regional policy makers, new projects.
- 5. Transdisciplinary learning community /network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity**
- This KER will create a platform (in form of summit, online platform, one time practical conference or other) to unite different stakeholders (local communities directly affected; local, national and international policy makers; NGOs; artists, academics) working on the case related topic. We aim to make this meaningful and relevant for all these stakeholders. This will probably happen in collaboration with the BioAgora project.
 - For several case studies, there may be pre-existing transdisciplinary learning communities or networks on transformative change for biodiversity. They can be in different levels from local to EU. We aim to connect them, which might be possible via international school systems (e.g. online platforms, course materials shared). By creating networks of networks, the community can be enabled.

4.2 Joint Exploitation plan(s)

Some of the exploitation plans in 4.1 are overlapping and applicable to more than one KER. This section includes a joint exploitation plan in terms of organization, further research, and promotion activities. Joint exploitation plans that overarch the KERs are:

- Joint dissemination event with our influencer and stakeholder board.
- Repository of transformative practices from each case. This involves adapted formats that can be developed for each stakeholder group, emphasizing aspects of their interests.

The joint exploitation of the BIOTraCes results does not include the set-up of new legal entities and does not include licensing or transferring IPR to partners or third parties. Therefore, formal post-project partnership agreements are not foreseen.

4.3 IP protection strategy

The European Commission requires participants Europe projects to: "...carefully consider and provide for adequate protection of results that promise to be of any potential for commercial and industrial exploitation", though formal protection is not mandatory. In our project plan, we aimed for all results and the KER to be open and free, because this increases impact of our results on policy, education and other studies and allows access for everyone. Therefore, automatic copyrights are the most important protection strategy for the author's works produced in BIOTraCes.

What's next?

Exploitation Roadmap and Intellectual Property Report - midterm

For now we aim for open results, however when it appears that some results must stay confidential to protect our case study partners, we will work according to our [data management plan](#).